

Reversible crystalline–amorphous phase transitions in silicon under electron-beam irradiation: A unified beam-heating perspective

Sung Bo Lee^{1,*}, Jaehun Kim², Jeongin Paeng³, Sung-Gyu Kang⁴, Jihye Kwon²,
Chi-Won Ahn⁵, Hyoung Seop Kim^{2,6,7}

¹Department of Materials Science and Engineering and Research Institute of Advanced Materials, Seoul National University, Seoul 08826, Republic of Korea

²Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology, Pohang, Republic of Korea

³Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials, Max-Planck-Straße 1, 40237 Düsseldorf, Germany

⁴Department of Materials Engineering and Convergence Technology, Gyeongsang National University, Jinju 52828, Republic of Korea

⁵Center for Nano-Material Technology Development, National Nanofab Center, Daejeon 34141, Republic of Korea

⁶Graduate Institute of Ferrous & Eco Materials Technology, Pohang University of Science and Technology (POSTECH), Pohang 37673, South Korea

⁷Advanced Institute for Materials Research (WPI-AIMR), Tohoku University, Sendai 980-8577, Japan

*Corresponding author. e-mail: boleee@snu.ac.kr

Abstract

Prior studies have independently reported electron-beam-induced crystallization of amorphous silicon (*a*-Si) and amorphization of crystalline silicon (*c*-Si), yet a unified explanation for these opposing transitions remains elusive. Conventional models invoke knock-on atomic displacement or bond breaking via electronic excitation, though it is counterintuitive that both could arise from the same athermal mechanisms. Using in situ transmission electron microscopy, we present the first direct observation of reversible transitions—from *a*-Si to *c*-Si and back—under constant irradiation. These findings challenge prevailing assumptions, suggesting distinct driving forces. To assess the possible contribution of beam heating to the driving forces, we employed a combination of Monte Carlo simulations and finite element analysis, incorporating Auger excitation as a plausible heating mechanism. The results reveal that heat accumulation becomes increasingly pronounced as thermal conductivity decreases from *c*-Si to *a*-Si. This trend suggests that crystallization in *a*-Si is driven by beam-induced heating, whereas amorphization in *c*-Si is primarily governed by knock-on atomic displacements. This study establishes a coherent framework for understanding electron–matter interactions and enables phase control in amorphous materials at the nanoscale.

Keywords: Silicon; Amorphization; Crystallization, Transmission electron microscopy; Beam heating

1. Introduction

Crystallization of amorphous materials is essential for modifying electrical, optical, and structural properties for applications like thin-film transistors, photovoltaics, and non-volatile memory devices [1–7]. This phase transition is generally thermally induced, necessitating high-temperature annealing or laser irradiation, as extensively evidenced in previous investigations of silicon (Si) and other phase-change materials [1,4–12].

Interestingly, electron beams in transmission electron microscopy (TEM) have been reported to induce various transitions, such as structural rearrangement, melting, and notably crystallization, in nanostructured Au and Bi and in amorphous oxides, even under nominally room-temperature conditions with beam currents of up to a few hundred nanoamperes (nA) at most [13–21]. These effects are generally attributed to beam-induced heating through inelastic electron–matter interactions [13–15,17–20], or in certain instances, to defect-assisted mechanisms [21], although the precise mechanisms have yet to be investigated.

In addition to the systems previously discussed, amorphous Si (*a*-Si) has been extensively studied for its crystallization properties under electron-beam irradiation [22,23], largely owing to its technological importance [1–3]. The work by Jenčič et al. [23] is particularly noteworthy for its systematic investigation of crystallization behavior under varying beam intensities. They observed that the crystallization rate decreased as beam energy increased, reaching a minimum near at the displacement threshold (~145 keV for Si) and then subsequently increasing again. This non-monotonic behavior was ascribed to a transition between excitation-dominated and displacement-dominated regimes, governed by the reduction of the inelastic scattering cross section at elevated energy.

To assess the role of beam-induced heating, Jenčič et al. [23] estimated the local temperature rise using electronic stopping power, which quantifies the energy loss of incident electrons due to inelastic interactions with atomic electrons [24]. Their calculation suggested a temperature increase of only a few kelvin, leading them to disregard thermal effects and instead attribute crystallization to athermal mechanisms such as knock-on displacement or bond breaking via electronic excitation. However, this interpretation introduces a mechanistic paradox: above the displacement threshold, crystalline Si (*c*-Si) amorphizes [25,26], whereas *a*-Si crystallizes [23]. It is implausible that *a*-Si crystallization is driven by the same athermal mechanisms, such as knock-on displacement or bond breaking via electronic excitation, that drive amorphization in *c*-Si.

Notably, the large body of prior research on thermally activated crystallization [1,4–12] underscores the essential role of heat in driving such phase transitions. This raises important questions about the physical effects of electron-beam irradiation in TEM, where localized energy deposition, even under low current, may produce sufficient thermal excitation to alter material phases.

The pronounced susceptibility of amorphous and nanostructured materials to such transformations [13–21] may stem from their intrinsically low thermal conductivity. In amorphous solids and low-dimensional systems, phonon transport is severely limited, impeding heat dissipation and enabling even modest energy input to generate significant local temperature rises. This context suggests that beam heating should be reconsidered as a viable mechanism, particularly in materials with poor thermal transport.

In this study, we address the mechanistic paradox underlying electron-beam-induced crystallization and amorphization in Si, using it as a model material. Through in situ

transmission electron microscopy (TEM) under constant irradiation conditions (300 keV, fixed current density), we observe that *a*-Si first crystallizes and subsequently reamorphizes within the same region, revealing sequential and reversible phase transitions. This reversibility has not been previously reported and cannot be accounted for by a single athermal mechanism, strongly indicating that distinct processes drive crystallization and amorphization under electron irradiation.

To resolve this paradox, we propose a unified framework supported by integrating finite element analyses (FEA) with Monte Carlo simulations, in which Auger excitation serves as the primary driver of localized heating. Owing to its large cross section and ability to deposit substantial energy, Auger excitation has been proposed to account for beam-induced mobility and melting phenomena in other materials [27–29]. Our simulations show that this mechanism becomes increasingly effective as thermal conductivity decreases, explaining why *a*-Si, with its disordered structure and low thermal conductivity, undergoes beam-induced crystallization, while *c*-Si, with much greater thermal conductivity, primarily experiences knock-on damage. These findings provide a coherent explanation for reversible phase transitions in Si and suggest that similar thermally assisted mechanisms may apply broadly to amorphous materials with limited heat conduction.

2. Experimental methods

We deposited an *a*-Si layer, with a thickness of ~300 nm, onto a commercially purchased Si(001) wafer (*c*-Si) by plasma-enhanced chemical vapor deposition. A conventional capacitively coupled reactor with a radio-frequency (RF) glow discharge at 13.56 MHz was used. A gas mixture of 80 sccm SiH₄ and 1000 sccm H₂ was introduced at a chamber pressure

of 2 Torr. Plasma was initiated by applying 100 W RF power, and the substrate temperature was maintained at 300°C.

TEM specimens were prepared using a dual-beam focused-ion beam system (Helios 5 UX, Thermo Fisher Scientific). Before milling, three protective layers were sequentially applied: a carbon coating outside the FIB system, followed by electron-beam-deposited Pt and FIB-deposited Pt layers inside the system, to minimize ion damage, prevent Ga implantation, and enhance mechanical stability. Milling was performed at 30 kV with beam currents of 22 nA to 41 pA, and final cleaning was conducted at 2 kV, 44 pA.

The FIB-prepared specimens were irradiated in a Cs-corrected, monochromated TEM (Themis Z, Thermo Fisher Scientific) at 300 keV, with a beam current of 4 nA and a circular beam diameter of 50 nm, yielding a current density of 204 A cm⁻². Observations were performed in situ during irradiation.

The chemical structure and composition of the specimens were analyzed using EELS and EDXS performed on a Themis Z microscope (Thermo Fisher Scientific) operated at 300 kV in scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) mode.

For EELS, spectrum imaging (SI) was conducted using dual EELS to simultaneously capture the low-loss and high-loss regions. A convergence semi-angle of 17.9 mrad and a collection semi-angle of 26.06 mrad were applied. The EELS data were acquired with an energy dispersion of 0.025 eV/channel and an energy resolution of 0.9 eV, using a 2.5 mm aperture. Low-loss spectra were acquired with an exposure time of 0.002 s per pixel, while high-loss spectra were acquired with 0.3 s per pixel. The SI maps were recorded with a spatial step size of 1–3 nm to capture fine structural variations.

For compositional analysis, STEM-EDXS was performed in SI mode using an 80 pm probe at 300 kV with a probe current of 76.8 pA. EDXS SI data were collected at a resolution of 1024×1024 pixels, with a pixel size of 149.5 pm and a dwell time of 5 μ s per pixel. Multiple frames were summed to enhance the signal-to-noise ratio.

Finite element analysis (FEA) was performed to estimate the temperature rise induced by beam irradiation, taking into account localized energy deposition via Auger excitation. Accurate modeling of beam-induced heating requires determining both the energy deposited by a single electron and its spatial distribution within the specimen. To this end, Monte Carlo simulations were carried out using CASINO (version 3.3.0.4) to trace electron trajectories and their interactions with the material. For the Auger excitation mechanism, we considered the major Si KLL Auger transition energy of 1621 eV [30] as the thermal input (Table I). A total of 10,000 Auger electrons were simulated with a beam diameter of 1 nm. The simulation volume was defined as $100 \text{ nm} \times 100 \text{ nm} \times 100 \text{ nm}$ and discretized into a $200 \times 200 \times 200$ grid, resulting in a voxel size of 0.5 nm per side—the smallest volumetric element in the simulation. These simulations account for both elastic scattering and inelastic collisions, enabling quantitative estimation of the energy loss per electron and the spatial extent of energy deposition. Resulting data serve as critical input parameters for defining the heat source in the FEA model.

For the Monte Carlo simulations, we used the following parameters: material densities were sourced from experimental data [31], and plasmon energies were taken from the literature for *c*-Si [32] and *a*-Si [33]. Elastic scattering cross sections were obtained from the ELSEPA database [34], while the stopping power (dE/dS) and ionization potentials were referenced from

the work of Joy and Luo [24]. A comprehensive summary of all parameters used is provided in Table I.

Table I. Parameters used in Monte Carlo simulations with CASINO.

	<i>c</i> -Si	<i>a</i> -Si
Density (g cm ⁻³)	2.3296 [31]	2.29 [31]
Plasmon energy (eV)	16.7 [32]	16.2 [33]
Auger electron energy (eV)	1621 [30]	

Thermal analysis was performed using finite element analysis (FEA). We used DC3D8 elements, which are eight-node linear hexahedral elements with trilinear interpolation of the temperature field. These elements are suitable for simulating heat conduction within solid media. A cylindrical heat source traversing the thin-film specimen was modeled, as described in detail below. To account for electron–phonon coupling during heating, a thermalization time of 10⁻¹² s (1 ps) was applied, based on literature values [27]. This implies that the maximum temperature was assumed to be reached 1 ps after energy deposition.

For the thermal calculations, material properties at 298 K were applied. For *c*-Si, the parameters included a density of 2.3296 g cm⁻³ [31], specific heat capacity of 0.712 J g⁻¹ K⁻¹ [31], and thermal conductivity of 22 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, measured for a 20 nm-thick Si layer [35], which approximates the ~50 nm thickness of the TEM specimens used in this study. This thermal conductivity value is significantly lower than the bulk value of 139 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹ [36]. This reduction accounts for nanoscale transport effects. For *a*-Si, the density was set to 2.29 g cm⁻³ [37], with the same specific heat capacity as in *c*-Si (0.712 J g⁻¹ K⁻¹) [38], and thermal conductivities of 1.5, 3, and 5 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, based on the thin-film measurement range [39–42].

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Reversible crystallization and amorphization under constant electron irradiation

The transformation began with a well-defined starting structure. Figure 1a presents an overview of the initial microstructure at the *a*-Si/*c*-Si interface. Figure 1b,c provide a higher-magnification view of the *a*-Si region prior to irradiation, confirming its fully amorphous nature through high-resolution imaging and the corresponding fast Fourier transforms (FFTs). After 10 min 40 s of irradiation (Fig. 1d), early signs of crystallization emerged within the central region. Crystallization continued to progress over time (Fig. 1e, 25 min 17 s) and reached its maximum extent at approximately 35 min 40 s (Fig. 1f), as evidenced by increasingly distinct diffraction spots in the FFT. By 45 min 30 s (Fig. 1g), the previously crystallized area began to reamorphize, indicating a reversal of phase under prolonged irradiation. The central region became fully amorphous again by 56 min 43 s (Fig. 1h). Figure 1i schematically illustrates the reversible crystallization and reamorphization of *a*-Si under constant irradiation, capturing the phase transitions observed in the same region without any change in beam conditions.

Fig. 1. (a) Initial microstructure at the *a*-Si/*c*-Si interface. (b) Overview of the *a*-Si region prior to irradiation, indicated by a dashed circle. (c) Higher-magnification view of the central area outlined by a square in (b), with the corresponding FFT shown in the inset. (d–h) Sequential HRTEM images of the same region, acquired at 10 min 40 s (d), 25 min 17 s (e), 35 min 40 s (f), 45 min 30 s (g), and 56 min 43 s (h). (i) Schematic illustration of the reversible crystallization–amorphization under constant prolonged irradiation.

Fig. 2. (a) Overview image acquired at 56 min 43 s. The higher-magnification view of the central irradiated area is shown in Fig. 1f. (b–d) Higher-magnification views of the peripheral regions outlined in (a), with corresponding FFTs.

Figure 2 presents the structure at the end of the irradiation sequence (56 min 43 s). A higher-magnification view of the central irradiated region is provided in Fig. 1f. In contrast, the peripheral areas (Fig. 2b–d) retained their crystalline structure, as indicated by the presence of lattice fringes and discrete diffraction spots in the corresponding FFTs.

As shown in Figs. 1 and 2, the irradiated region exhibited distinct spots in the fast Fourier transforms (FFTs), indicating crystallization. The FFT displayed in Fig. 1f, acquired at 35 min 40 s when the crystallization degree reached its maximum, is reproduced in Fig. S1 as a

representative case for spot indexing. To aid indexing, we superimposed green circles onto this FFT, corresponding to the expected diffraction rings for diamond-cubic Si with a lattice parameter of 0.543 nm. Although reference circles were not applied to all FFTs, the same trend was observed across them. See the detailed indexing and reference matching in the Supplementary Material, Section 1.

Figure 3 shows the time-dependent structural evolution of a *c*-Si region under electron-beam irradiation. In the initial state (Fig. 3a), the region exhibited typical *c*-Si atomic structure along the [1 1 0] zone axis. After 12 min 23 s of irradiation (Fig. 3b), early beam-induced modifications became apparent, including selective sputtering and the formation of stacking faults. By 23 min 2 s (Fig. 3c), localized amorphous pockets had formed, as revealed by the enlarged image of the boxed region and the corresponding FFT. Continued irradiation resulted in complete amorphization of the irradiated region by 35 min 31 s (Fig. 3d), evidenced by the disappearance of diffraction spots and the appearance of a diffused ring pattern in the FFT. No further structural change was observed at 48 min 15 s (Fig. 3e), indicating that the region remained fully amorphous despite prolonged exposure.

Fig. 3. (a) Overview of the initial state, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and its corresponding fast Fourier transform (FFT) (right panel). The irradiated area (50 nm in diameter) is marked by a dashed circle. (b) Overview at 12 min 23 s. (c) Overview at 23 min 2 s, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and corresponding FFT (right panel). (d) Overview at 35 min 31 s, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and corresponding FFT (right panel). (e) Overview at 48 min 15 s, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and corresponding FFT (bottom panel).

3.2. Beam-induced oxygen enrichment

Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) measurements revealed that, prior to irradiation, both *a*-Si and *c*-Si contained comparable oxygen concentrations, approximately 4 at.%, as shown in Fig. S2 and Table S1. To assess whether electron-beam exposure altered the composition, EDXS was also performed on the regions corresponding to the final states in Fig. 1h (56 min 43 s, *a*-Si) and Fig. 3e (48 min 15 s, *c*-Si) (see also Fig. 4 and Table S2). Both area mapping and line profile analyses revealed a substantial increase in oxygen content within the irradiated regions. Specifically, area mapping showed an increase from the initial ~4 at.% (Fig. S2 and Table S1) to approximately 24 at.% in *a*-Si and 37 at.% in *c*-Si (Fig. 4 and Table S2). This trend was also clearly reflected in the line composition profiles (Fig. 4c,f), indicating pronounced beam-induced oxygen incorporation, regardless of whether the initial phase was *a*-Si or *c*-Si.

Fig. 4. Panels (a–c) correspond to the initial *a*-Si and (d–f) to the initial *c*-Si. (a,d) High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) images acquired after prolonged electron-beam irradiation. (b,e) Corresponding elemental intensity maps showing oxygen (red) and silicon (green). (c,f) Composition line profiles extracted along the arrows shown in (b) and (e), respectively, with integration widths indicated.

To investigate the structural and chemical changes induced by electron-beam irradiation, we performed both low-loss and high-loss electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS) on *a*-Si and *c*-Si in their initial and irradiated states (Fig. 5). For the initial state, EELS was conducted at the *a*-Si/*c*-Si interface (Fig. 5a,b). The darker contrast at the interface in the ADF and ADF survey images is attributed to partial delamination between *c*-Si and *a*-Si, already present in the as-deposited specimen. The annular dark-field (ADF) images of the irradiated *a*-Si and *c*-Si regions, corresponding to the EDXS mapping areas shown in Fig. 4a and 4d, are presented in Fig. 5c and 5d, respectively.

Fig. 5. (a) Annular dark-field (ADF) survey image of the *a*-Si/*c*-Si interface in the initial state. (b) ADF image of the spectrum imaging (SI) region in (a). (c) ADF image of the SI region in *a*-Si after prolonged electron-beam irradiation, acquired from the same region analyzed in Fig. 4a. (d) ADF image of the SI region in *c*-Si after prolonged irradiation, acquired from the same region analyzed in Fig. 4d. (e) Low-loss EELS spectra acquired from the boxed regions in (b–d), representing the initial and irradiated states of *a*-Si and *c*-Si. A reference spectrum from amorphous SiO₂ (*a*-SiO₂) [52,53] is included for comparison. (f) High-loss EELS spectra acquired from the same regions, with a reference spectrum from *a*-SiO₂ [53,56].

In the low-loss EELS spectra (Fig. 5e), the initial *a*-Si and *c*-Si exhibited bulk plasmon peaks at 16.59 and 16.74 eV, respectively. Our measured plasmon energy values is well consistent with earlier studies, which report bulk plasmon energies for *c*-Si typically ranging

from 16.7 to 16.8 eV [43–50]. In contrast, *a*-Si generally shows plasmon energies near 16.3 eV [43], a lower value than for *c*-Si that is often linked to its disordered structure and lower electron density. Our measured value, 16.59 eV, is consistent with this and supports the expected behavior for *a*-Si.

In contrast, the irradiated regions exhibited a noticeable shift of the bulk plasmon peak to higher energies: 16.9 eV for *a*-Si and 17.1 eV for *c*-Si (Fig. 5e). A broad hump centered near 10 eV is observed in all spectra, as indicated by downward arrows in Fig. 5e, and is attributed to surface plasmon losses [33,45]. These losses become more pronounced in the thinner irradiated regions, where surface excitations at the specimen–vacuum interface dominate as bulk scattering diminishes.

Notably, the bulk plasmon peaks in the irradiated regions exceeded those of the initial *a*-Si and *c*-Si. This upshift is attributed to oxidation of the Si matrix, as corroborated by EDXS results (Fig. 4 and Table S2). The bulk plasmon energy of Si increases with oxygen content: pure Si exhibited a plasmon energy of 16.7–16.8 eV, while that of SiO and SiO₂ rises to ~19 eV and ~23 eV, respectively [47,49,50]. Bell and Ley demonstrated that increasing oxygen content leads to a monotonous rise in plasmon loss energy [51]. In Fig. 5e, the reference spectrum of amorphous SiO₂ (*a*-SiO₂), which peaks near 23 eV [52,53] is included for comparison.

In the high-loss EELS spectra (Fig. 5f), the Si L_{2,3}-edge features of both *a*-Si and *c*-Si were analyzed in their initial and irradiated states. In the initial state, *a*-Si and *c*-Si both exhibited similar edge onsets at 99.4 eV, followed by peaks at 101.2 eV and 101.4 eV, respectively. The peak intensity at the edge is lower in *a*-Si compared with *c*-Si, consistent with previous reports [54,55]. After prolonged irradiation, the *a*-Si region showed an edge onset at 99.5 eV and a peak at 101.4 eV, both comparable to the initial values. In contrast, the irradiated *c*-Si region

exhibited an edge onset at 99.3 eV but lacked a well-defined peak following the onset, because both the irradiated *a*-Si and *c*-Si regions were fully amorphous.

For comparison, the high-loss EELS spectrum of *a*-SiO₂, adapted from Batson [56] and Ewels et al. [53], shows an edge onset at 104 eV, a shoulder at 106 eV, a sharp peak at 108 eV, and a broad peak centered around 115 eV, which are typical for *a*-SiO₂ [54,57,58]. The same shoulder and peaks characteristic of *a*-SiO₂ appear in the spectra of both irradiated *a*-Si and *c*-Si, as indicated by vertical lines in Fig. 5f. This suggests beam-induced oxidation and the formation of Si–O bonding environments in the irradiated regions.

3.3. Thermal origin of opposing phase transitions under electron irradiation

Over the course of ~1 hour of irradiation (Figs. 1–3), we observed that the initial *a*-Si first crystallized into *c*-Si, then reamorphized back to *a*-Si. Meanwhile, the initial *c*-Si underwent amorphization.

Since the present acceleration voltage of 300 keV far exceeds the minimum incident-electron energy for knock-on displacement in *c*-Si (146 keV, corresponding to a minimum displacement energy of 13 keV [26]), *c*-Si is highly susceptible to knock-on atomic displacement at 300 keV, which result in its amorphization, as shown in Fig. 3. The subsequent reamorphization of the crystallized region in Figs. 1h and 2 is again consistent with knock-on damage, as for the amorphization in Fig. 3.

However, invoking the same knock-on mechanism to explain the crystallization of *a*-Si under identical irradiation conditions (as in Fig. 1) appears implausible. The different responses to electron-beam irradiation, i.e., crystallization of *a*-Si and amorphization of *c*-Si, point to important distinctions in how these phases interact with electrons. Amorphous Si (*a*-Si) has a

disordered structure and significantly lower thermal conductivity [39–42] than for *c*-Si [35,36]. This means it is not as good at dispersing localized energy as *c*-Si. This makes *a*-Si more likely to build up heat quickly. This characteristic drives us to investigate whether localized beam heating could explain the observed crystallization.

3.4. Insignificant effects of beam heating through energy loss by incident electrons

First, we consider beam heating effects through energy loss by incident electrons. As previously mentioned, for the electron energy loss effect, we referred to the work by Jenčič et al. [23], who reported that the temperature rise resulting from energy dissipation by the incident electron beam was negligible, on the order of just a few degrees Celsius. Their estimation was based on a steady-state thermal equilibrium between energy deposition and heat dissipation via conduction, a generally acceptable methodology. Nonetheless, there are limitations in directly applying their calculations to our crystallization in *a*-Si. The problem lies in their use of *c*-Si thermal conductivity when evaluating heat loss, whereas our study involves *a*-Si, which has a significantly lower thermal conductivity.

To obtain a more accurate estimate under our specific experimental conditions (300 keV, 4 nA), we carried out an analytical derivation of the temperature increase, ΔT , using a modified model introduced by Egerton et al. [25]. As in the model used by Jenčič et al. [23], it is also based on a steady-state condition in which heat generation is balanced by heat loss via radial conduction. The temperature rise is given by

$$\Delta T = \frac{I\langle E \rangle}{4\pi\kappa\lambda} \left[0.58 + 2\ln\left(\frac{2R_0}{d}\right) \right],$$

where I is the beam current (4 nA), $\langle E \rangle$ is the average energy loss per incident electron in Si at 300 keV (19.65 eV), λ is the inelastic mean free path of an incident electron (124.4 nm), κ is

the thermal conductivity of *a*-Si ($1.5 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) [42], d is the beam diameter (50 nm), and R_0 is the characteristic radial conduction length (typically 30 μm).

With these parameters, the calculated ΔT is approximately 0.5 K, confirming that beam-induced heating due to inelastic energy loss is minimal. It goes without saying that the temperature rise would be even smaller in *c*-Si, given its much higher thermal conductivity ($22 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$).

3.5. Auger excitation as the dominant beam-heating mechanism

The issue of beam heating beyond the effect of energy loss of incident electrons has not been effectively addressed to date, largely because no convincing mechanism for delivering sufficient heat input has been proposed. In this work, we identify Auger excitation as a compelling candidate: it features a high cross section and can deliver nanometer-scale energy spikes sufficient to drive atomic rearrangement and phase transitions, as introduced earlier [27–29]. Auger electrons deposit a substantial portion of their energy into plasmon excitations, and into generating low-energy secondary electrons ($<50 \text{ eV}$), which subsequently contribute to localized beam heating. As noted above, the major Si KLL Auger transition energy of 1621 eV [30] was used as the input energy for Monte Carlo simulations. Low-energy secondary electrons transfer their energy to the lattice on the order of 10^{-12} s ($\sim 1 \text{ ps}$), a timescale corresponding to electron–phonon coupling [27]. Therefore, we set the FEA thermalization time to 1 ps.

At 300 keV, the Si KLL Auger cross section is $\sim 10^{-21} \text{ cm}^2$ ($\sim 1,000 \text{ barns}$) [59,60]. Based on this value, the estimated frequency of Auger events under our experimental conditions (4 nA, 300 keV, 50 nm beam diameter) is $\sim 6.1 \times 10^6$ events per second, corresponding to an

average interval of $\sim 1.64 \times 10^{-7}$ s (0.164 μ s) between successive events. The detailed estimation procedure is outlined in the Supplementary Material, Section 3.1.

We will present our thermal analysis results from Monte Carlo simulations and FEA in the following sections. Then, in Section 3.5.5, we will discuss in detail the dominance of Auger excitation as the primary driver of beam heating, relative to other emitted electrons.

3.5.1. Monte Carlo simulations as a prerequisite to FEA

Thermal analysis was primarily conducted using FEA based on localized energy deposition via Auger excitation. As noted above, Monte Carlo simulations are a necessary precursor to FEA, as they provide essential input parameters—such as the trajectory length of a single Auger electron and the energy absorbed by the medium—for accurately defining the heat source in the FEA framework.

Fig. 6. (a) Energy distribution map obtained from Monte Carlo simulations (CASINO) for a 1 nm-diameter electron beam composed of 10,000 electrons incident on Si specimens (*c*-Si and *a*-Si). (b) Corresponding cumulative energy deposition profile with increasing penetration depth.

To quantify the extent of beam energy deposited within the specimen, Monte Carlo simulations were conducted using 10,000 electrons, each with an incident Auger energy of 1,621 eV. The total input energy was therefore 16,210 keV. The simulations modeled Auger electrons generated at the top surface of the specimen and propagating into the material. For both *c*- and *a*-Si, the maximum penetration depth was limited to 50 nm, matching the specimen thickness. The resulting energy distribution map (Fig. 6a) shows a blob-like shape elongated along the depth axis, clearly reflecting the cumulative effects of both inelastic and elastic scattering during electron penetration. These effects include energy loss due to inelastic scattering and trajectory deflection primarily caused by elastic scattering. From this distribution, the cumulative energy deposition profile was extracted (Fig. 6b). Within this depth, the absorbed energy amounted to 13,298 keV for *c*-Si and 13,194 keV for *a*-Si, indicating that approximately 82% of the total beam energy was deposited in the sample in both cases. The slight variation between the two structures reflects differences in scattering behavior due to atomic ordering, which influence the trajectories and inelastic interaction rates of incident electrons.

However, the energy distribution map reflect the aggregate energy deposited by all 10,000 electrons, not the energy deposited per electron. It shows the statistical distribution of deposited energy density, with each voxel reflecting the expected value of energy deposited by multiple

electrons. In this context, the data in Fig. 7 is more relevant for illustrating energy deposition during the traversal of a single Auger electron, as discussed below.

3.5.2. Energy-loss profiles by Monte Carlo simulations

Figure 7a presents the energy loss profile as a function of distance traveled for 25 individual electron trajectories for *c*-Si. On average, each electron loses approximately 1571 eV over a 76.5 nm path. The incident electrons, initially at 1621 eV, gradually lose energy with increasing depth due to inelastic scattering. The slope of this energy–distance curve defines the electronic stopping power, which increases with depth, reflecting the well-known energy dependence of stopping power—lower-energy electrons lose energy more rapidly. Although the curve is nonlinear, the overall trend may be approximated by linear interpolation, yielding an average stopping power of $\sim 20.54 \text{ eV nm}^{-1}$.

Figure 7b shows the decrease of Auger electron energy with distance traveled for *a*-Si. Using the same criteria as applied to *c*-Si, the electronic stopping power for *a*-Si is equivalent to 20.18 eV nm^{-1} ($= 1571 \text{ eV}/77.8 \text{ nm}$). That is, the energy deposited by a single Auger electron is given by the product of the average electronic stopping power and the distance traveled.

Fig. 7. (a) Energy loss as a function of distance traveled for 25 electron trajectories in *c*-Si. (b) Energy loss profile for Auger electrons in *a*-Si.

3.5.3. Physical rationale of the cylindrical energy-deposition model

While the energy distribution map (Fig. 6a) and cumulative profile (Fig. 6b) represent the collective behavior of 10,000 electrons, these do not directly provide the energy deposition volume per electron. In reality, an electron follows a straggling path—typically entering the specimen through the top surface and exiting through the bottom—depositing energy intermittently along a narrow, thread-like track.

Therefore, we approximated the energy deposition region of a single electron as a narrow cylindrical filament, an approach grounded in the physics of electron–matter interactions. As an Auger electron traverses the material, it loses energy mainly by exciting plasmons, which decay into secondary electrons (SEs), and these SEs, typically below 50 eV, contribute to the majority of the deposited energy [61,62], as sketched in Fig. S3, which leads to local heating [27]. The radial extent of energy deposition is governed by the transport length of secondary electrons (SEs). This is closely linked to the effective attenuation length (EAL)—the 1/e decay length of detected electron intensity for a given geometry, accounting for both inelastic and

elastic scattering [63]. SEs generated from Auger cascades span 0–50 eV; because they undergo frequent elastic scattering and rapidly lose directionality, the EAL provides a suitable measure of their radial transport prior to thermal diffusion. For modeling purposes, the EAL was evaluated at a representative energy of 50 eV. For 50 eV electrons, the effective attenuation length (EAL) is ~ 0.25 nm. Since $\sim 95\%$ of the intensity decays within $3 \times \text{EAL}$, we assumed that nearly all SE energy is dissipated within this distance. Thus, the cylindrical heat-source diameter was set to $6 \times \text{EAL}$ (~ 1.5 nm), representing the full radial range of SE energy deposition. This geometry was then used in finite element analysis (FEA) to calculate the transient temperature rise from localized beam heating.

3.5.4. FEA-based temperature modeling

Based on the Monte Carlo simulation results, we hypothesized that the energy deposited by a single electron can be modeled as confined within a narrow cylindrical volume, representing a thread-like trajectory extending vertically through the specimen. The height of the cylinder was set to 50 nm, corresponding to the specimen thickness, and its diameter to 1.5 nm, as sketched in Fig. S4.

For *c*-Si, using the average stopping power of 20.54 eV nm^{-1} derived from Fig. 7a, the deposited energy within this cylinder is estimated to be 1027 eV (I.e., $20.54 \text{ eV nm}^{-1} \times 50 \text{ nm}$). Similarly, for *a*-Si, using the average stopping power of 20.18 eV nm^{-1} derived from Fig. 7b, the deposited energy within this cylinder is estimated to be 1009 eV.

Alternatively, for *c*-Si, the full energy loss of 1571 eV over a 76.5 nm trajectory, as shown in Fig. 7a, may be used to define the deposition profile. In this case, a cylindrical heat source with a 1.5 nm diameter and a height of 76.5 nm contains the full 1571 eV. Similarly, for *a*-Si, a

cylinder with the same diameter and a height of 77.8 nm contains the full 1571 eV, as shown in Fig. 7b. This approach preserves the same energy density (i.e., deposited energy per unit volume) as the 50 nm-high model. Since both configurations yield equivalent thermal effects in the finite element analysis, we adopt the 50 nm-high cylinder model, which directly matches the physical specimen thickness.

Fig. 8. (a) Full finite element analysis (FEA) model with dimensions of $200 \text{ nm} \times 200 \text{ nm} \times 50 \text{ nm}$. (b) Quarter-symmetric FEA model with dimensions of $100 \text{ nm} \times 100 \text{ nm} \times 50 \text{ nm}$.

Figure 8 shows the position and dimensions of the cylindrical heat source and the full mesh model used for FEA, respectively. To enable fast analysis, a quarter-symmetric three-dimensional model was constructed with dimensions of 100 nm in length and width, and 50 nm in thickness (Fig. 8b). The mesh size within the irradiated region was refined to 0.0025 nm

to capture localized effects, with a gradual transition to a coarser mesh of 0.1 nm in the surrounding areas to optimize computational efficiency (Fig. 8).

As shown in Figs. 9 and 10, the temperatures measured at the center of the cylindrical heat source are approximately 693 K, 550 K, and 473 K for *a*-Si with thermal conductivities of 1.5, 3, and 5 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively, and 352 K and 306 K for *c*-Si with thermal conductivities of 22 and 139 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, respectively. These results clearly demonstrate that lower thermal conductivity, as in *a*-Si, leads to less efficient heat dissipation and consequently higher peak temperatures.

Fig. 9. Quarter-symmetric temperature distribution models at 1 ps for *a*-Si (thermal conductivity: 1.5, 3, and 5 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹) and *c*-Si (22 and 139 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹).

Fig. 10. Temperature contour maps in the $y = 0$ plane at 1 ps for (a–c) a -Si with thermal conductivities of 1.5, 3, and 5 $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$, and (d,e) c -Si with thermal conductivities of 22 and 139 $\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$. The point $(x, z) = (0, 0)$ corresponds to the center of the cylindrical heat source. (f) Temperature–time profiles measured at the center of the cylindrical heat source.

3.5.5. Why Auger electrons dominate beam heating: a rule of thumb from electronic stopping power

Incident electrons at 300 keV contribute negligibly to beam heating, whereas Auger electrons, generated by these incident electrons, can contribute substantially. This distinction is also explained by the concept of electronic stopping power. The stopping power increases as the acceleration voltage decreases because slower electrons interact more strongly with the electronic clouds of atoms, leading to more frequent inelastic scattering events. For Si (density: 2.3 g cm^{-3} , both c -Si and a -Si), the stopping power of 300 keV incident electrons is only 0.44 eV nm^{-1} , as reported in Ref. 64 [64], resulting in minimal energy deposition. In contrast, Auger electrons at 1621 eV exhibit a much higher stopping power of $\sim 20 \text{ eV nm}^{-1}$, as estimated by Monte Carlo simulations, leading to substantially greater energy deposition and pronounced

beam-induced local heating (Figs. 9 and 10). Therefore, in addition to the analytical calculation presented in Section 3.4, this estimation clearly demonstrates that 300 keV incident electrons make a negligible contribution to beam heating, whereas Auger electrons play a significant role.

Primary beam electrons—whether elastically (backscattered or diffracted) or inelastically scattered—retain nearly the full incident energy [65] and therefore have low electronic stopping power; their direct contribution to beam heating is negligible compared with the Auger-initiated low-energy cascade.

3.5.6. Comparison with previous work

In our earlier work [28,29], we adopted a simplified model in which the entire energy of an Auger electron was assumed to be deposited within a spherical region whose diameter corresponded to the inelastic mean free path (IMFP) of the electron. While this provided a useful starting point, further consideration suggests that it may not fully capture the nature of energy deposition at this scale. Williams [27] also considered the Auger energy to be concentrated within the total volume of each gold (Au) nanodot to clarify the movement of the nanodots under electron-beam irradiation. However, in practice, Auger electrons lose energy progressively through multiple inelastic scattering events as they travel through a medium. These interactions lead to a more distributed pattern of energy loss along the electron's trajectory, rather than a concentrated release within a single localized volume. We deem the present approach more realistic and rigorous.

3.6. Formation of a ring-shaped crystalline region and the role of knock-on atomic displacement

During electron-beam irradiation using a circular beam profile, the amorphous silicon region underwent progressive crystallization within the irradiated zone, as shown in the sequential HRTEM image series (Figs. 1–2). With continued exposure, the central area of the irradiated region began to reamorphize, while the surrounding area remained crystalline. This process resulted in a ring-shaped crystalline structure encircling an amorphous core (Fig. 2).

The formation of the ring-shaped crystalline region is attributed to the Gaussian distribution of current density in the circular electron beam. The current density peaks at the center and then diminishes toward the periphery. Consequently, the centrally crystallized region undergoes increased knock-on atomic displacements and reamorphization occurs earlier, while the periphery, subjected to a lesser cumulative dose, maintains its crystalline structure. This selective phase reversal generates the annular crystalline region depicted in Fig. 2.

3.7. Correlation between oxygen incorporation and beam heating effects

Another notable finding from this study is that both *a*-Si and *c*-Si underwent pronounced oxidation after prolonged electron-beam irradiation, as revealed by EDXS and EELS (Figs. 4 and 5), with oxygen content in the irradiated amorphous region reaching up to ~40 at.% (Table S2) and forming Si suboxides. To comprehend the origin of this oxygen enrichment, we first consider the displacement energy thresholds. In the context of fused silica, the minimum displacement energies are approximately 15 eV for oxygen and 40 eV for silicon [66]. These values correspond to electron threshold energies of approximately 100 keV for oxygen and 375 keV for silicon. Given that the present 300 keV acceleration voltage lies within this range, it permits selective displacement of O atoms, potentially facilitating the dissociation of SiO₂ into Si. Furthermore, silicon oxides exhibit vulnerability to electron-stimulated desorption via the

Knotek–Feibelman mechanism [67], wherein Auger excitation induces positive charges on O ions, reducing their binding energy and thus facilitating oxygen loss [68,69].

The observed oxygen enrichment is unequivocally not attributable to knock-on displacement or desorption processes. Instead, it also provides definitive evidence that beam-induced heating was the primary driver, with localized thermal effects promoting oxidation by residual O₂ in the TEM chamber (vacuum $\sim 10^{-5}$ Torr), consistent with previously reported beam-heating-driven oxidation behavior in manganese [70].

To evaluate an additional phase change (i.e., crystallization) following the amorphization shown in Figs. 1–3, extended irradiation beyond 1 h is required. However, this approach is challenging because the specimens had already undergone significant thinning. Electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS) log-ratio measurements [71] showed that the initial thicknesses, 47.74 nm for *a*-Si and 48.91 nm for *c*-Si (Fig. 5a,b), were reduced to 28.27 nm and 10.86 nm, respectively, in the irradiated regions at the final time points (Fig. 5c,d), primarily due to electron-beam-induced sputtering. Minor perforation was also observed in the *c*-Si specimen after EDXS analysis (Fig. 4d).

It is worth noting that the observed oxygen enrichment in the irradiated regions (Figs. 4 and 5) suggests potential structural evolution under prolonged exposure. We postulate that the progressive formation of Si–O bonds increasingly inhibits further crystallization of *a*-Si. Such crystallization would require the breaking of these bonds and reorganization of the silicon network, which are energetically unfavorable under continued oxygen incorporation by beam heating during irradiation. By contrast, under reducing conditions or in an ultrahigh vacuum environment, the outcome may differ. This hypothesis warrants further investigation.

4. Concluding remarks

To conclude, this study demonstrates that electron-beam-induced phase transitions in Si arise from fundamentally distinct mechanisms. These transitions can be understood within a unified thermal framework, in which Auger-excitation-driven heating plays a dominant role and is modulated by the contrasting thermal conductivities of Si's amorphous and crystalline phases. Using in situ TEM under identical irradiation conditions, we observed reversible transformations: the initial *a*-Si crystallized and subsequently reamorphized, while the initial *c*-Si underwent amorphization.

The combination of FEA and Monte Carlo simulations revealed that heat accumulation becomes more pronounced as thermal conductivity decreases, explaining why heating effects dominate in *a*-Si, whereas *c*-Si primarily experiences displacement-driven amorphization. In addition, we observed significant oxidation in the irradiated region, indicating the involvement of thermally activated processes and reinforcing the role of localized beam heating.

Together, these findings provide a coherent mechanistic understanding of electron-beam-induced phase transitions. While *a*-Si served as a model system, the underlying principles likely extend to a broad class of amorphous materials with intrinsically low thermal conductivity, where localized beam heating can drive crystallization. More broadly, our results refine the current understanding of electron-matter interactions and establish a foundation for nanoscale phase control through electron-beam-mediated mechanisms.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Sung Bo Lee: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis,

Conceptualization. **Jihye Kwon:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Chi Won Ahn:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis. **Hyung Seop Kim:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Formal analysis.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

S.B.L. received financial support from the Korea Basic Science Institute under the R&D program (Project No. A412550) supervised by the Ministry of Science and ICT (MSIT, Republic of Korea). S.B.L. was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the MSIT [2019R1A2C2002073 (RIAM)], by the Ministry of Education [RS-2023-00240516 (RIAM)] and by the Ministry of Trade, Industry, and Energy [RS-2024-00455529 (RIAM)]. H.S.K. was supported by the National Research Foundation of Korea (NRF) grant funded by the Korea government (MSIP) (NRF-2022R1A5A1030054).

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at

References

- [1] S. Uchikoga, Low-temperature polycrystalline silicon thin-film transistor technologies for system-on-glass displays, *MRS Bull.* 27 (2002) 881–886, <https://doi.org/10.1557/mrs2002.277>.
- [2] O. Astakhov, R. Carius, F. Finger, Y. Petrusenko, V. Borysenko, D. Barankov, Relationship between defect density and charge carrier transport in amorphous and microcrystalline silicon, *Phys. Rev. B* 79 (2009) 104205, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.79.104205>.
- [3] M.A. Green, The path to 25% silicon solar cell efficiency: History of silicon cell evolution, *Prog. Photovoltaics: Res. Appl.* 17 (2009) 183–189, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pip.892>.
- [4] M. Wuttig, N. Yamada, Phase-change materials for rewriteable data storage, *Nat. Mater.* 6 (2007) 824–832, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nmat2009>.
- [5] M. Le Gallo, A. Sebastian, An overview of phase-change memory device physics, *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 53 (2020) 213002, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6463/ab7794>.
- [6] Y. Cheng, Q. Yang, J. Wang, T. Dimitriadis, M. Schumacher, H. Zhang, M.J. Müller, N. Amini, F. Yang, A. Schoekel, J. Pries, R. Mazzarello, M. Wuttig, H.-B. Yu, S. Wei, Highly tunable β -relaxation enables the tailoring of crystallization in phase-change materials, *Nat. Commun.* 13 (2022) 7352, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-022-35005-x>.
- [7] S. Wintersteller, O. Yarema, D. Kumaar, F.M. Schenk, O.V. Safonova, P.M. Abdala, V. Wood, M. Yarema, Unravelling the amorphous structure and crystallization mechanism of GeTe phase change memory materials, *Nat. Commun.* 15 (2024) 1011, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-45327-7>.

- [8] S. Sriraman, S. Agarwal, E.S. Aydil, D. Maroudas, Mechanism of hydrogen-induced crystallization of amorphous silicon, *Nature* 418 (2002) 62–65, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature00866>.
- [9] L. Lermusiaux, A. Mazel, A. Carretero-Genevri, C. Sanchez, G.L. Drisko, Metal-induced crystallization in metal oxides, *Acc. Chem. Res.* 55 (2022) 171–185, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.accounts.1c00592>.
- [10] G. Marcins, J. Butikova, I. Tale, B. Polyakov, R. Kalendarjov, A. Muhin, Crystallization processes of amorphous Si by thermal annealing and pulsed laser processing, *IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng.* 23 (2011) 012035, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/23/1/012035>.
- [11] W.-E. Hong, J.-S. Ro, Kinetics of solid phase crystallization of amorphous silicon analyzed by Raman spectroscopy, *J. Appl. Phys.* 114 (2013) 073511, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4818949>
- [12] D.S. Dhungana, E. Bonaventura, C. Martella, C. Grazianetti, A. Molle, Solid phase crystallization of amorphous silicon at the two-dimensional limit, *Nanoscale Adv.* 5 (2023) 668–674, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2NA00546H>.
- [13] D.S. Dhungana, E. Bonaventura, C. Martella, C. Grazianetti, A. Molle, Solid phase crystallization of amorphous silicon at the two-dimensional limit, *Nanoscale Adv.* 5 (2023) 668–674, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D2NA00546H>.
- [14] T. Yokota, M. Murayama, J.M. Howe, In situ transmission electron microscopy investigation of melting in submicron Al-Si alloy particles under electron-beam irradiation, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 91 (2003) 265504, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.91.265504>.

- [15] H. Zheng, J.B. Rivest, T.A. Miller, B. Sadtler, A. Lindenberg, M.F. Toney, L.W. Wang, C. Kisielowski, A.P. Alivisatos, Observation of transient structural-transformation dynamics in a Cu_2S nanorod, *Science* 333 (2011) 206–209, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1204713>.
- [16] K. Higuchi, T. Tokunaga, T. Sato, T. Yamamoto, Electron-beam-induced crystallization of amorphous gallium oxide thin films using scanning transmission electron microscopy, *Cryst. Growth Des.* In press (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.cgd.5c00148>.
- [17] A.K. Gerasimova, V.Sh. Aliev, G.K. Krivyakin, V.A. Voronkovskii, Comparative study of electron-beam crystallization of amorphous hafnium oxides HfO_2 and HfO_x ($x = 1.82$), *SN Appl. Sci.* 2 (2020) 1273, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42452-020-3102-8>.
- [18] J. Shim, J.A. Rivera, R. Bashir, Electron beam induced local crystallization of HfO_2 nanopores for biosensing applications, *Nanoscale* 5 (2013) 10887, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3NR02608F>.
- [19] C. Kaito, T. Harada, T. Miyano, A new crystallographic shear structure in tin oxide, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* 22 (1983) L394–L396.
- [20] V.V. Roddatis, D.S. Su, F.C. Jentoft, R. Schlogl, Temperature- and electron-beam-induced crystallization of zirconia thin films deposited from an aqueous medium: a transmission electron microscopy study, *Philos. Mag.* 82 (2002) 2825–2839, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01418610208240068>.
- [21] Y. Li, L. Zang, D.L. Jacobs, J. Zhao, X. Yue, C. Wang, In situ study on atomic mechanism of melting and freezing of single bismuth nanoparticles, *Nat. Commun.* 8 (2017) 14462, <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms14462>.

- [22] W.-Q. Huang, S.-R. Liu, Z.-M. Huang, T.-G. Dong, G. Wang, C.-J. Qin, Silicon nanocrystal growth under irradiation of electron beam, *Sci. Rep.* 5 (2015) 16682, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep16682>.
- [23] I. Jenčič, M.W. Bench, I.M. Robertson, M.A. Kirk, Electron beam induced crystallization of isolated amorphous regions in Si, Ge, GaP, and GaAs, *J. Appl. Phys.* 78 (1995) 974–982, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.360764>.
- [24] D. C. Joy, S. Luo, An empirical stopping power relationship for low-energy electrons, *Scanning* 11 (1989) 176–180, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sca.4950110404>.
- [25] R.F. Egerton, P. Li, M. Malac, Radiation damage in the TEM and SEM, *Micron* 35 (2004) 399–409, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micron.2004.02.003>.
- [26] A.Yu. Konobeyev, U. Fischer, Yu.A. Korovin, S.P. Simakov, Evaluation of effective threshold displacement energies and other data required for the calculation of advanced atomic displacement cross-sections, *Nucl. Energy Technol.* 3 (2017) 169–175, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nucet.2017.08.007>.
- [27] P. Williams, Motion of small gold clusters in the electron microscope, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 50 (1987) 1760–1762, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.97739>.
- [28] S.B. Lee, S.G. Kang, J. Jung, S. Sung, S.J. Yoo, H.N. Han, Lattice shear and non-random rotation of Au nanoparticles under electron-beam irradiation, *Acta Mater.* 241 (2022) 118387, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actamat.2022.118387>.
- [29] S.B. Lee, J.Y. Chae, H.N. Han, Nanoscale liquid Al phase formation through beam heating of MgAl₂O₄ in TEM, *Nanoscale Adv.* 6 (2024) 2830–2837, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D4NA00011K>.

- [30] K.D. Childs, B.A. Carlson, L.A. LaVanier, J.F. Moulder, D.F. Paul, W.F. Stickle, D.G. Watson, Handbook of Auger Electron Spectroscopy: A Book of Reference Data for Identification and Interpretation in Auger Electron Spectroscopy, 3rd Ed., edited by C. L. Hedberg (Physical Electronics, Inc., Eden Prairie, MN, 1995).
- [31] D.R. Lide, CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics, 89th Ed. (CRC Press, Boca Raton, 2008).
- [32] J. Stiebling, H. Raether, Dispersion of the volume plasmon of silicon (16.7 eV) at large wave vectors, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 40 (1978) 1293–1295. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.40.1293>
- [33] J.-M. Costantini, J. Ribis, Analysis of plasmon loss peaks of oxides and semiconductors with the energy loss function, *Materials* 16 (2023) 7610, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16247610>.
- [34] F. Salvat, A. Jablonski, C.J. Powell, ELSEPA—Dirac partial-wave calculation of elastic scattering of electrons and positrons by atoms, positive ions and molecules, *Comput. Phys. Commun.* 165 (2005) 157–190. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2020.107704>
- [35] W. Liu, M. Asheghi, Phonon–boundary scattering in ultrathin single-crystal silicon layers, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 84 (2004) 3819–3821, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1741039>.
- [36] E. Yamasue, M. Susa, H. Fukuyama, K. Nagata, Thermal conductivities of silicon and germanium in solid and liquid states measured by non-stationary hot wire method with silica coated probe, *J. Cryst. Growth* 234 (2002) 121–131, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0248\(01\)01673-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-0248(01)01673-6).

- [37] J.S. Custer, M.O. Thompson, D.C. Jacobson, J.M. Poate, S. Roorda, W.C. Sinke, F. Spaepen, Density of amorphous Si, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 64 (1994) 437–439, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.111121>.
- [38] B.L. Zink, R. Pietri, F. Hellman, Thermal conductivity and specific heat of thin-film amorphous silicon, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 96 (2006) 055902, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.96.055902>.
- [39] H.J. Goldsmid, M.M. Kaila, G.L. Paul, Thermal conductivity of amorphous silicon, *Phys. Status Solidi A* 76 (1983) K31–K33, <https://doi.org/10.1002/pssa.2210760156>.
- [40] H. Wada, T. Kamijoh, Thermal conductivity of amorphous silicon, *Jpn. J. Appl. Phys.* 35 (1996) L648–L650.
- [41] D. Tanisawa, Y. Shionozaki, T. Takizawa, A. Yamaguchi, H. Murotani, M. Takashiri, Ultralow thermal conductivity of amorphous silicon–germanium thin films for alloy and disorder scattering determined by 3ω method and nanoindentation, *Appl. Phys. Expr.* 17 (2024) 011005, <https://doi.org/10.35848/1882-0786/ad14f1>.
- [42] S. Moon, M. Hatano, M. Lee, C.P. Grigoropoulos, Thermal conductivity of amorphous silicon thin films, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transf.* 45 (2002) 2439–2447, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0017-9310\(01\)00347-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0017-9310(01)00347-7).
- [43] R.F. Egerton, *Electron Energy-Loss Spectroscopy in the Electron Microscope*, 2nd Ed. (Plenum, New York, 1996).
- [44] A. Barker, B. Sapkota, J.P. Oviedo, R. Klie, Automated plasmon peak fitting derived temperature mapping in a scanning transmission electron microscope, *AIP Adv.* 11 (2021) 035330, <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0039864>.

- [45] F. Yubero, S. Tougaard, E. Elizalde, J.M. Sanz, Dielectric loss function of Si and SiO₂ from quantitative analysis of REELS spectra, *Surf. Interf. Anal.* 20 (1993) 719–726, <https://doi.org/10.1002/sia.740200817>.
- [46] K.A. Mkhoyan, T. Babineca, S.E. Maccagnano, E.J. Kirkland, J. Silcox, Separation of bulk and surface-losses in low-loss EELS measurements in STEM, *Ultramicroscopy* 107 (2007) 345–355, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2006.09.003>.
- [47] D. Kot, G. Kissinger, M.A. Schubert, A. Sattler, Current stage of the investigation of the composition of oxygen precipitates in Czochralski silicon wafers, *ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol.* 6 (2017) N17–N24, <https://doi.org/10.1149/MA2016-02/26/1776>.
- [48] J. Wong, D.A. Jefferson, T.G. Sparrow, J.M. Thomas, R.H. Milne, A. Howie, E.F. Koch, High resolution electron microscopic and spectroscopic characterization of semi-insulating polycrystalline silicon and its interface with single crystal silicon, *Appl. Phys. Lett.* 48 (1986) 65–67, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.96763>.
- [49] G. Kissinger, D. Kot, M. Klingsporn, M.A. Schubert, A. Sattler, T. Müller, Investigation of the copper gettering mechanism of oxide precipitates in silicon, *ECS J. Solid State Sci. Technol.* 4 (2015) N124–N129, <https://doi.org/10.1149/2.0151509jss>.
- [50] C.H. Chen, J. Silcox, R. Vincent, Electron-energy losses in silicon: Bulk and surface plasmons and Čerenkov radiation, *Phys. Rev. B* 12 (1975) 64–71, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.12.64>.
- [51] F.G. Bell, L. Ley, Photoemission study of SiO_x ($0 \leq x \leq 2$) alloys, *Phys. Rev. B* 37 (1988) 8383–8392, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.37.8383>.

- [52] M.C. Cheynet, T. Epicier, Structural and chemical analysis of a model Si–SiO₂ interface using spatially resolved electron energy-loss spectroscopy, *Philos. Mag.* 84 (2004) 1753–1771, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14786430310001659507>.
- [53] P. Ewels, T. Sikora, V. Serin, C.P. Ewels, L. Lajaunie, A complete overhaul of the electron energy-loss spectroscopy and X-ray absorption spectroscopy database: eelsdb.eu, *Microsc. Microanal.* 22 (2016) 717–724, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1431927616000179>.
- [54] H. Kabbara, C. Noël, J. Ghanbaja, K. Hussein, D. Mariotti, V. Švrček, T. Belmonte, Synthesis of nanocrystals by discharges in liquid nitrogen from Si–Sn sintered electrode. *Sci. Rep.* 5 (2015) 17477, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep17477>.
- [55] M. Schade, B. Fuhrmann, A. Chassé, F. Heyroth, M. Roczen, H.S. Leipner, Distinction between amorphous and crystalline silicon by means of electron energy-loss spectroscopy, *Appl. Phys. A* 120 (2015) 393–399, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-015-9201-5>.
- [56] P.E. Batson, Current trends for EELS studies in physics, *Microsc. Microanal. Microstruct.* 2 (1991) 395–402, <https://doi.org/10.1051/mmm:0199100202-3039500>.
- [57] K. Kimoto, T. Sekiguchi, T. Aoyama, Chemical shift mapping of Si L and K edges using spatially resolved EELS and energy-filtering TEM, *J. Electron Microsc.* 46 (1997) 369–374, <https://doi.org/10.1093/oxfordjournals.jmicro.a023532>.
- [58] L.A.J. Garvie, P.R. Buseck, Bonding in silicates: Investigation of the Si L_{2,3} edge by parallel electron energy-loss spectroscopy, *Am. Mineral.* 84 (1999) 946–964, <https://doi.org/10.2138/am-1999-5-631>.
- [59] X. Llovet, C.J. Powell, F. Salvat, A. Jablonski, Cross sections for inner-shell ionization by electron impact, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data* 43 (2014) 013102.

- [60] X. Llovet, F. Salvat, D. Bote, F. Salvat-Pujol, A. Jablonski, C.J. Powell, NIST Database of Cross Sections for Inner-Shell Ionization by Electron or Positron Impact Version 1.0 (National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), Gaithersburg, MD, 2014).
- [61] C.R. Arumainayagam, H.-L. Lee, R.B. Nelson, D.R. Haines, R.P. Gunawardane, Low-energy electron-induced reactions in condensed matter, *Surf. Sci. Rep.* 65 (2010) 1–44. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfrep.2009.09.00>.
- [62] R.F. Egerton, Control of radiation damage in the TEM, *Ultramicroscopy* 127 (2013) 100–108. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultramic.2012.07.006>.
- [63] C.J. Powell, A. Jablonski, NIST Electron Effective-Attenuation-Length Database (SRD 82), Version 1.3, National Institute of Standards and Technology, Gaithersburg, Maryland, 2011.
- [64] M. J. Berger, J. S. Coursey, M. A. Zucker, J. Chang, Stopping Power and Range Tables for Electrons, Positrons, and Helium Ions, National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) Standard Database 124 (2017) <https://www.nist.gov/pml/stopping-power-range-tables-electrons-protons-and-helium-ions>.
- [65] D.B. Williams, C.B. Carter, *Transmission Electron Microscopy*, Springer, New York, 2009.
- [66] F. Mota, M.-J. Caturla, J.M. Perlado, E. Dominguez, A. Kubota, Threshold energy of formation of an oxygen vacancy defect in SiO₂ by atomic displacements using molecular dynamics, *Fusion Eng. Des.* 75–79 (2005) 1027–1030, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fusengdes.2005.06.215>.

- [67] M.L. Knotek, P.J. Feibelman, Stability of ionically bonded surfaces in ionizing environments, *Surf. Sci.* 90 (1979) 78–90, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0039-6028\(79\)90011-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0039-6028(79)90011-6).
- [68] G.S. Chen, C.B. Boothroyd, C.J. Humphreys, Electron-beam-induced damage in amorphous SiO₂ and the direct fabrication of silicon nanostructures, *Philos. Mag. A* 78 (1998) 491–506, <https://doi.org/10.1080/01418619808241915>.
- [69] M.L. Knotek, J.E. Houston, Study of the stepwise oxidation and nitridation of Si(111): Electron stimulated desorption, Auger spectroscopy, and electron loss spectroscopy, *J. Vac. Sci. Technol. B* 1 (1983) 899–914, <https://doi.org/10.1116/1.582710>.
- [70] S.B. Lee, J. Kwon, H.S. Kim, Electron-beam induced Mn oxidation in TEM: Insights into the heating effect of Auger oxidation, *Micron* 190 (2025) 103763, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.micron.2024.103763>.
- [71] T. Malis, S.C. Cheng, R.F. Egerton, EELS log-ratio technique for specimen-thickness measurement in the TEM, *J. Electron Microsc. Tech.* 8 (1988) 193–200, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jemt.1060080206>.

Table and figure captions

Table I. Parameters used in Monte Carlo simulations with CASINO.

Fig. 1. (a) Initial microstructure at the *a*-Si/*c*-Si interface. (b) Overview of the *a*-Si region prior to irradiation, indicated by a dashed circle. (c) Higher-magnification view of the central area outlined by a square in (b), with the corresponding FFT shown in the inset. (d–h) Sequential HRTEM images of the same region, acquired at 10 min 40 s (d), 25 min 17 s (e), 35 min 40 s (f), 45 min 30 s (g), and 56 min 43 s (h). (i) Schematic illustration of the reversible crystallization–amorphization under constant prolonged irradiation.

Fig. 2. (a) Overview image acquired at 56 min 43 s. The higher-magnification view of the central irradiated area is shown in Fig. 1f. (b–d) Higher-magnification views of the peripheral regions outlined in (a), with corresponding FFTs.

Fig. 3. (a) Overview of the initial state, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and its corresponding fast Fourier transform (FFT) (right panel). The irradiated area (50 nm in diameter) is marked by a dashed circle. (b) Overview at 12 min 23 s. (c) Overview at 23 min 2 s, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and corresponding FFT (right panel). (d) Overview at 35 min 31 s, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and corresponding FFT (right panel). (e) Overview at 48 min 15 s, with an enlarged view of the boxed region and corresponding FFT (bottom panel).

Fig. 4. Panels (a–c) correspond to the *a*-Si and (d–f) to the initial *c*-Si. (a,d) High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) images acquired after prolonged electron-beam irradiation. (b,e) Corresponding elemental intensity maps showing oxygen (red) and silicon (green). (c,f)

Composition line profiles extracted along the arrows shown in (b) and (e), respectively, with integration widths indicated.

Fig. 5. (a) Annular dark-field (ADF) survey image of the *a*-Si/*c*-Si interface in the initial state. (b) ADF image of the spectrum imaging (SI) region in (a). (c) ADF image of the SI region in *a*-Si after prolonged electron-beam irradiation, acquired from the same region analyzed in Fig. 4a. (d) ADF image of the SI region in *c*-Si after prolonged irradiation, acquired from the same region analyzed in Fig. 4d. (e) Low-loss EELS spectra acquired from the boxed regions in (b–d), representing the initial and irradiated states of *a*-Si and *c*-Si. A reference spectrum from amorphous SiO₂ (*a*-SiO₂) [52,53] is included for comparison. (f) High-loss EELS spectra acquired from the same regions, with a reference spectrum from *a*-SiO₂ [53,56].

Fig. 6. (a) Energy distribution map obtained from Monte Carlo simulations (CASINO) for a 1 nm-diameter electron beam composed of 10,000 electrons incident on Si specimens (*c*-Si and *a*-Si). (b) Corresponding cumulative energy deposition profile with increasing penetration depth.

Fig. 7. (a) Energy loss as a function of distance traveled for 25 electron trajectories in *c*-Si. (b) Energy loss profile for Auger electrons in *a*-Si.

Fig. 8. (a) Full finite element analysis (FEA) model with dimensions of 200 nm × 200 nm × 50 nm. (b) Quarter-symmetric FEA model with dimensions of 100 nm × 100 nm × 50 nm.

Fig. 9. Quarter-symmetric temperature distribution models at 1 ps for *a*-Si (thermal conductivity: 1.5, 3, and 5 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹) and *c*-Si (22 and 139 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹).

Fig. 10. Temperature contour maps in the $y = 0$ plane at 1 ps for (a–c) *a*-Si with thermal conductivities of 1.5, 3, and 5 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹, and (d,e) *c*-Si with thermal conductivities of 22 and 139 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹. The point $(x, z) = (0, 0)$ corresponds to the center of the cylindrical heat source.
(f) Temperature–time profiles measured at the center of the cylindrical heat source.

Supplementary Material

**Reversible crystalline–amorphous phase transitions in silicon under
electron-beam irradiation: A unified beam-heating perspective**

Sung Bo Lee^{1,*}, Jaehun Kim², Jeongin Paeng³, Sung-Gyu Kang⁴, Jihye Kwon²,

Chi-Won Ahn⁵, Hyoung Seop Kim^{2,6,7}

¹Department of Materials Science and Engineering and Research Institute of Advanced Materials, Seoul
National University, Seoul 08826, Republic of Korea

²Department of Materials Science and Engineering, Pohang University of Science and Technology, Pohang,
Republic of Korea

³Max Planck Institute for Sustainable Materials, Max-Planck-Straße 1, 40237 Düsseldorf, Germany

⁴Department of Materials Engineering and Convergence Technology, Gyeongsang National University, Jinju
52828, Republic of Korea

⁵Center for Nano-Material Technology Development, National Nanofab Center,
Daejeon 34141, Republic of Korea

⁶Graduate Institute of Ferrous & Eco Materials Technology, Pohang University of Science and Technology
(POSTECH), Pohang 37673, South Korea

⁷Advanced Institute for Materials Research (WPI-AIMR), Tohoku University,
Sendai 980-8577, Japan

*Corresponding author. e-mail: bole@snu.ac.kr

1. Fast Fourier transform (FFT) of irradiated regions

As shown in Figs. 1 and 2, the irradiated regions display distinct spots in the fast Fourier transforms (FFTs), which are characteristic of crystallization. To support phase identification, a representative FFT acquired after 35 min 40 s of irradiation (Fig. 1f) is shown in Fig. S1. For indexing purposes, we overlaid green circles on this FFT, marking the expected positions of diffraction rings for diamond-cubic silicon (Si) with a lattice parameter of 0.543 nm. These rings correspond to the $\{1\ 1\ 1\}$, $\{2\ 2\ 0\}$, $\{3\ 1\ 1\}$, $\{4\ 0\ 0\}$, $\{3\ 3\ 1\}$, $\{4\ 2\ 2\}$, $\{3\ 3\ 3\}/\{5\ 1\ 1\}$, $\{4\ 4\ 0\}$, and $\{5\ 3\ 1\}$ planes, progressing outward from the center.

The diffraction spots observed in the experiment closely matched these reference rings, indicating that the crystallized phase adopts the same structure as bulk Si.

Fig. S1. Representative FFT after 35 min 40 s of irradiation (from Fig. 1f), with green circles overlaid to mark the expected diffraction rings for diamond-cubic Si (lattice parameter: 0.543 nm).

2. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS)

Fig. S2. (a) High-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) image showing the *a*-Si/*c*-Si interface prior to irradiation. (b,c) Corresponding energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDXS) elemental maps of oxygen (O) and silicon (Si), respectively.

Table S1. Atomic compositions of oxygen and silicon in the initial, unirradiated *a*-Si and *c*-Si regions. Elemental concentrations (at.%) were measured by EDXS in the rectangular areas marked in Fig. S2.

Element	<i>a</i> -Si	<i>c</i> -Si
O	4.63	4.31
Si	95.37	95.69

Table S2. Atomic compositions of oxygen and silicon in the irradiated *a*-Si and *c*-Si regions. Elemental concentrations (at.%) were determined by EDXS within the square regions marked in Fig. 4b (*a*-Si) and Fig. 4e (*c*-Si). Oxygen content increased to 23.94 at.% in *a*-Si and 36.86 at.% in *c*-Si, indicating substantial beam-induced oxygen incorporation.

Element	<i>a</i> -Si	<i>c</i> -Si
O	23.94	36.86
Si	76.06	63.14

Fig. S3. Schematic of an Auger electron path and the resulting secondary electron emission.

3. Finite element analysis (FEA)

Fig. S4. Schematics showing the position and dimensions of the cylindrical heat source. In the upper-left schematic, the red dot indicates the source location. In the cross-sectional view, the red rectangle represents the cylindrical heat source, with its diameter exaggerated relative to its thickness for visibility. The white dashed line marks the centerline of the heat source.

3.1. Estimation of the Auger event rate

The Auger event rate in *a*-Si was evaluated according to $R = \sigma\Phi N$, where σ denotes the effective cross section for the relevant Auger process, Φ is the current density of primary incident electrons, and $N (= nV)$ is the number of atoms contained in the irradiated volume.

The Si KLL Auger cross section (σ) at 300 keV is $\sim 10^{-21} \text{ cm}^2$ [1,2]. The beam current density (Φ) at 4 nA over a 50 nm diameter corresponds to approximately 204 A cm^{-2} , or $\sim 1.27 \times 10^{21} \text{ electrons s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$. For a material density of 2.3 g cm^{-3} (for *a*-Si), the corresponding atomic density is $n \approx 4.9 \times 10^{22} \text{ atoms cm}^{-3}$. With a circular beam of 50 nm diameter and a specimen thickness of 50 nm, the irradiated volume is $9.8 \times 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^3$, containing approximately 4.8×10^6 atoms. Substituting the aforementioned σ and Φ yields an Auger event rate of $R \approx 6.1 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The corresponding mean interval between successive Auger events, given by the reciprocal of R , is $\Delta t \approx 1.64 \times 10^{-7} \text{ s}$ (0.164 μs).

4. Transient heating dynamics under Auger events

Our FEA results (Fig. 6) indicate that the maximum temperature, peaking at 1 ps, rapidly decreased to room temperature within a few additional picoseconds. Since this cooling time is much shorter than the estimated interval between Auger events (0.164 μ s), thermal accumulation is unlikely to occur under successive Auger excitations. In other words, each temperature rise is temporally discrete, as the system returns to thermal equilibrium well before subsequent excitations occur. Auger excitation injects effective thermal energy capable of driving atomic rearrangements. The heat generated is transient and localized. This localized heating, while brief, can still create the right conditions for phase transformation processes like crystallization.

5. Effects of specimen and beam drift on irradiated area

The residual crystalline regions were observed outside the nominal 50 nm irradiation circle (Fig. 2), indicating an expansion of the affected area. This enlargement likely resulted from a combination of specimen drift and beam drift. Although the TEM's piezo-driven stage is designed to compensate for specimen movement, it cannot fully correct positional shifts in amorphous regions due to the lack of lattice references. Occasional beam drift also contributed to the gradual outward expansion of the irradiated zone.

References

- [1] X. Llovet, C.J. Powell, F. Salvat, A. Jablonski, Cross sections for inner-shell ionization by electron impact, *J. Phys. Chem. Ref. Data* 43 (2014) 013102.
- [2] X. Llovet, F. Salvat, D. Bote, F. Salvat-Pujol, A. Jablonski, C.J. Powell, NIST Database of Cross Sections for Inner-Shell Ionization by Electron or Positron Impact Version 1.0 (National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), Gaithersburg, MD, 2014).